

The role of people, process and place in new approaches to designing for service

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Abstract

In this paper we explain how a human centered approach has been applied to the field of service design—more specifically health services. Emotion plays a large role in the perception of any service, but unlike a travel agency or a car dealership, health services are produced and consumed when a person has a problem. With health services, the consumer is much more likely to be experiencing stressful or unhappy emotions even before seeking out assistance. This paper illustrates a project where human centered design methods such as environmental research, participatory design, conceptual prototyping and evaluative testing were used to influence change in established and relatively fixed service systems. We offer a look at how services are designed today and details about how the approach applied evolved from that investigation and practical design work with Carnegie Mellon University Student Health Services.

Keywords: Service design, user centered design, interaction design, participatory design

1. Introduction

Carnegie Mellon is a University in Pittsburgh Pennsylvania in the United States. CMU serves more than 5000 students on several campuses. The Student Health Services (SHS) at Carnegie Mellon offers a variety of basic medical services to university students much like a doctor's office. The SHS deals with prevention and treatment of minor illnesses and injuries. The facility has a dedicated entrance even though it is located on the first floor of a large dormitory. The space that SHS is housed in was not designed for them from scratch. Lack of conscious design with regard to the space has led to the staff to find ways to improvise with some processes and procedures; these improvisations impact the student patient's experience. The staff of the SHS is professional and caring and wanted an opportunity to improve their work and the emotional well being of patients. Health Service is rarely considered an emotional process and yet, our preliminary research showed us that it is always very emotional. We saw an opportunity to help the staff have more control of their own work process and at the same time improve the emotional well being of the student patients.

1.1 Service design as a response to the challenges with Student Health Services at Carnegie Mellon

In recent years, there has been a dramatic shift in many of the world's major economies from manufacturing products to delivering services. What used to be a one-time-sell is becoming a persistent service concept with the objective of fulfilling customer needs over time. When products become services, they no longer stand-alone. The selling point is no longer about the what the product "is" or "does" but what the product can "do for you".

In our view, services are activities or events that form a 'product' through an interaction with representatives of the service organization, the customer, and any mediating technology (Rayport & Jaworski, 2005). Services are also 'performances' as choreographed interactions manufactured at the point of delivery that form a process and co-produce value, utility, satisfaction, and delight in response to human needs (Edvardsson, Gustafsson, Johnson, & Sandén, 2000).

Design is the act of conceiving, planning and constructing elements into wholes that form communications, products, services, environments or systems so that they are appropriate to human situations. Service design is a form of architecture that involves processes rather than bricks and mortar. The perception of the quality of a service will be influenced by a myriad of elements functioning together (Edvardsson, Gustafsson, Johnson, & Sandén, 2000). The service designer's goal is to be able to identify and respond to customer expectations by designing all the elements or resources that have the potential to influence the experience. These elements constitute the service interface and usually include people, facilities and information in and around the service (Rayport & Jaworski, 2005). In our experience as interaction designers, user centered design techniques are useful when identifying user needs and expectations. We believe that applying both user centered and participatory design methods can help make user needs and expectations explicit. In our academic practice, these tools are merged with other service design methods to guide the design process.

The school of design at Carnegie Mellon engaged in two service design projects with the Student Health Center: a three-week exercise and an Interaction Design Master Thesis.

2. Three-week exercise

A small team of design students conducted the exercise. The team observed for two periods of two hours, and surveyed twenty-one students about their experience with SHS in order to find areas for improvement. In addition to the student interviews, the team interviewed with the assistant manager of the clinic and conducted a quick benchmarking comparing the SHS clinic with two other clinics in the universities nearby through short observations and on-site interviews with fifteen students.

Student interviews suggested two negative emotional reactions to the SHS clinic: feeling mistreated and feeling ignored. Most of the time, these emotions were attributed to long waiting times without any explanation of the wait by the staff and the occasional cold

interaction with the clinical staff. Uncertainty about how to access the services as well as not knowing how long the wait would be. Two brainstorming sessions helped the team of students move from documenting what the experience was to exploring opportunities for what could be different. Concepts for service improvement were mapped in a two by two matrix (Fig. 1) to contrast potential impact on the service experience vs. cost of implementation.

SELECTED DIRECTIONS
IMPACT VS COST

Figure 1: Impact vs. cost

High impact & low cost concepts were embodied in a scenario and presented to the director of the clinic, along with the research methodology and a high-level summary of the interviews. The presentation concluded the three-week project. The three-week exercise was centered on the patients' discomfort and its influencers. The clinic's management accepted the ideas and made some attempts of implementation. However,

traces of the re-design were hard to see in the staff's interpretation of the concepts. The management implementation revealed big dissimilarities between the staff and the student's experiences. In the three-week exercise the staff was only peripherally involved. Because of that, they found it difficult to connect to the sources of discomfort and consequently, were unable to relate to the suggested improvements.

The differences between how the student team understood the work of the clinic and the ways things worked in reality was subtle in theory but in practice, very different.

3. A staff-driven service design

The three-week exercise results suggested that in order to achieve a successful intervention, the designer should use a different model of communication (Forester, 1985). The second iteration of design development with the SHS was undertaken as a Master Thesis project in the fall of 2005. Instead of focusing on the patients, this time the effort was centered on the service providers and the organization with the goal of developing improvements more likely to be realized.

Edgar Schein (Schein, 1993) points out that the organization and its culture are in many ways created by the people inside it. This position suggests that if design is to succeed in influencing organizational change, designers must understand how organizations work at all levels. In this case, understanding the motivations and culture of the caregivers inside SHS provided ways of effectively influencing and transforming the organizational management and service processes through design.

SHS service is primarily a human-human service; it is a completely organic system—created every day by the people inside it. A design intervention should suggest improvements and provide tools for the internal stakeholders so that changes are not only executed and effective but also embraced and sustainable over time. To be successful, any change must come from inside and be backed up by experience; design development should be 'for the people' and be done 'by the people'. In other words, the elements

designed need to be personal not only as a service for the students but more importantly for the service creators and owners—the staff.

3.2 Understanding SHS people, processes and place

The first step was to secure the participation and support of the Director of the clinic. The goals for the second iteration were explained and the Director gave permission and full access to the entirety of the clinic, staff, and procedures.

3.2.1 Exploration

The Master Thesis research program included 18 paper based student surveys that were filled on-site. The main objective was to gain a deeper knowledge of what the SHS experience was for the student-patients. At the same time, patient experience journals were completed by three different students, all of them with a different set of goals when accessing the clinic.

One-on-one interviews were conducted with all the full-time staff. The first objective of the interview was to introduce the designer and the project in an open and non-threatening conversation. The second objective was to learn about each staff member personally and their role in the clinic. Interviews were designed to get a better understanding of the clinic's inner workings, to aid the mapping of cliques within the social network of SHS and their organizational culture. Interview topics ranged from the tasks the staff members performed, to friendships with peers, likes and dislikes about their job and finally, their ideas for improvement.

3.2.2 Narrowing the scope

Areas for improvement as perceived by the staff were compared with the patient's complaints collected in the paper surveys and interviews. The Advice and Appointment (A&A) area surfaced as difficult both from the student side and the staff side. Being the first point of contact a patient encounters, the A&A is a primary contributor to the student's perception of clinic's service delivery quality. This position made A&A an ideal focus for the design intervention.

3.2.3 Making emotional states explicit

Narrowing the scope to A&A made it easier for the designer to solicit the staff's perceptions and expectation of a core SHS process. A three-day experience journal (Fig. 2) was developed and distributed to the staff members who engage in the A&A process. The purpose of the journal was to have the staff explicitly map the tasks and emotional states they confronted each day. In addition, the journal was intended to get the staff thinking about their emotions.

Figure 2: Task | three-day emotion journal. Subjects were asked to identify and capture their mood, to heighten their awareness of what was good, bad and could be different.

The results revealed that most of the participants were happy performing their main tasks and unhappy about additional tasks. This also gave us an insight into what particular positions feel to the people performing them. Four out of eight caregiver journals showed considerable discomfort while performing paperwork tasks. One of them was remarkable because the main source of discomfort was related to solving the student parent's inquiries. Data was overlapped with the one-on-one staff interviews. This confirmed the need to lighten administrative tasks and allow the caregivers to focus on their primary roles.

3.2.4 Customer expectations and journey

It was clear from the student interviews and surveys that patients' discomfort was related to unfulfilled expectations. These expectations are often built by a patient's previous experience in other clinical settings (such as a hospital or a doctor's office).

Nevertheless, similarities between the SHS and a hospital clinic or a doctor's office are only related to the industry they belong to. The work practice in the SHS is very different than other clinical settings. These findings suggest that guiding the student's initial expectations could improve their perception of the overall experience at the SHS.

A walk-a-mile study was conducted to identify the influential factors on the patient experience. In this study, a researcher approached the clinic with a goal, such as scheduling an appointment, and navigated the space in order to accomplish the goal. Our research indicated that for a first-time student-patient, the SHS clinic is a mystery. Getting service in the clinic becomes a confusing process; just locating the clinic is hard to do. An idea that surfaced early was that transparency through point-of-need information resources at the registration process might be able to better-set student expectations.

Figure 3: Patient Journey for the A&A area

To receive medical attention, a student goes through a process or a "Journey" (Fig. 3). The Student Journey consists of a set of steps followed to be able to speak to a nurse or access other services at the clinic. The journey continues all the way through the service even after the student leaves the clinic. Mapping of the primary customer journey and the touch points associated with it helped us identify particular breakdowns in the process

and opportunities for improvement. In the A&A area, the journey is composed by nine steps. Two of the steps were inside the nurse's office and consisted of clinical triage and prescriptions. Due to privacy concerns the clinical steps were not included in the redesign and our project addressed only the seven non-clinical steps in the journey.

3.2.6. "Town Meeting"

The designer scheduled a participatory work session (Sanders & William, 2001), with all the staff of the clinic. The session started with a brief introduction of the project and its goals. The concept of Student Journeys was illustrated in order to show how changes in the journey could improve the perception of the SHS. The staff was assured that they were the 'experts'. We explained that the ideas presented were by no means fixed or absolute, but there spark ideas from them.

To introduce the activity in a non-threatening but controlled fashion, the designer made flipbooks. Flipbooks are analog and tangible, and have the added ability to reveal their content over time. The flipbooks (Fig. 4) recreated the student-patient's journey, what the environment offered and finally some rough sketches around what could be done to improve the experience. The presented problems were big and general; the improvements illustrated by the sketches were particular. The town meeting allowed us to involve the staff on the project and to show how small and individual contributions affect the perception of the clinic and its service as a whole.

Figure 4: Flipbook structure

During the meeting, participants were asked to number themselves from 1 to 4 to break up the different cliques and to ensure diverse skills in the teams. As the teams opened the flipbooks, they were asked to talk about what they observed in the images and to later

sketch and “complete” the improvements (Fig. 5). The simplicity of the flipbooks and sketches made it easy for each team to actively relate to content of the activity and not see the suggested solutions as imposed or fixed but one where they had a direct and continuous influence.

Figure 5: Flipbook with sketches

After the teams were done discussing and sketching, they were asked to explain their work to the rest of the group. Each team proudly presented their insights and solutions. The staff was engaged, very enthusiastic, and participative. The discussion even expanded to other problems inside the clinic that were not represented in the flipbooks.

3.2.7 Concept Refinement

The Town Meeting merged the staff’s insights with those of the designer. Special effort was made to make the staff contributions highly visible. The refined sketches (Fig. 6) were presented to the staff one week after. The staff was asked to review the ideas again and make notes on the new sketches wherever they felt a change or correction was needed. Feedback from this stage was tabulated and the “sign in process” improvements were selected for on-site evaluation and testing.

Figure 6: refined sketches

3.2.8 On-Site testing

A full-scale mock-up was created and placed in the clinic for evaluation. The mock-up consisted of a series of didactic signs to guide students through the process of accessing one of four services at the clinic. The signs were paired with custom sign-in sheets, which had been redesigned to gather particular information as required by the caregivers. The sign-in sheets had a small survey attached to it. The survey consisted of a series of facial expressions. Students were asked to circle the facial expression that best matched their mood and satisfaction level about the service improvements. We also asked if they found the new forms useful.

Figure 7: Full-scale mock-ups

Signage and surveys were installed for three weeks (Fig. 7). Eighteen out of twenty-six students was happy with the improvements and felt more comfortable while accessing the service through the new process. After this testing the designer attended to a full staff meeting where the staff was asked to reflect back about what they thought was working and what was not working in the redesigned process. They were also asked to express if they perceived any difference in their mood and individual productivity. The test materials and associated processes were simplified based on the feedback collected both from the patient survey and the staff meeting. In the new version some of the pathways were combined to lighten the process.

Figure 8: Full-scale mock-ups (2nd iteration)

A second model was tested for one week (Fig. 8), six surveys were collected and the A&A staff was interviewed again. This second iteration performed better and some parts of the redesign were so popular among the front line staff that when the testing was over, these parts were enthusiastically merged with the existing process.

4. Design Principles & Service Specifications

Based on the testing results, we developed a set of design implications. The final design specification provides theoretical tools to approach the improvements but also a step-by-step program that can be implemented over time as the financial resources become available. The first step of the re-design focuses on a print ready version of the new sign-in process. This signage is designed to help manage student expectations by providing truly relevant information all along the process.

Figure 8: Sketch for future scenario

Figure 9: New customer Journey

The latter steps involve reconditioning the space (Fig. 8 and 9) and the implementation of electronic records. In order to provide resources for its realization, the project documentation identifies a set of academic contacts inside the university that as part of their course's projects can help with the re-design implementation. Upon the delivery and presentation of the documentation, the clinic's management as well as the staff were excited about how their new understanding had influenced the changes.

5. Conclusions

Our experience with the SHS project allowed us to better understand the role and influence of people in complex service environments. Reflecting on it, we offer a set of principles that can aid the guidance of future work on the field of human-to-human services.

5.1 Managing expectations

The perception of any service is deeply linked to the expectations about it. When designing for service, it is crucial to identify the factors influencing the stakeholders' expectations. By making visible the invisible through service & process transparency designed interventions can positively affect expectations around a service. For a service to be perceived as good it needs to fulfill not only the client's expectations but also the ones of the service provider.

5.2 Organic systems and emotion

In a human-to-human service delivery system the services are produced and delivered on the fly each and every day. The emotional state of the service provider will influence their ability to provide not only specialized help but also to make it in a warm and caring way. People in technical fields are actively engaged in the delivery of the service but have little time for reflection on how it might be qualitatively improved.

5.3 Clear and tangible interventions

Service design interventions must be made explicit to all the people within the organization, even those not directly participating. Each step, its reasons and desired outcomes must be made clear to the participants. Prototyping can play an important role in making tangible the types of changes ideated in this type of intervention.

5.4 Participation and emotional investment

User-centered design techniques can provide the means for actively reflecting on the service delivery impact. We learned that design interventions informed by participatory design must be allowed, implemented and supported by the management. The participants are not only investing time but also creativity and intelligence. This involvement results in an emotional bondage through ownership, not only of the particular ideas but more importantly, the ideals and philosophy driving the project. If the resulting improvements are not visible to the staff, the design intervention can damage the staff's perception of the organization and the role they play in it.

5.5 Ownership and sustainability

Participation and ownership in the design process by the service providers is key to sustainability and change. The results of the SHS interventions began the moment the service providers became actively and personally involved in the process. Participants began reflecting about not only how the system influences them, but also became explicitly aware of their roles and influence on the overall quality of the service delivery, relating to the process as a positive driver of change. As a result of applying an interaction & participatory design approach to the SHS project, its outcomes are organic and sustainable organizational changes that are embodied in the people, processes and places of the Student Health Services.

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